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Abstract:

This deliverable provides guidelines detailing the different roles intended for the SSH Open Marketplace’s sustainability. The governance of the SSH Open Marketplace is studied through individuals’ role necessary to ensure continuous curation, operation, and maintenance of the service and through the dedicated governing bodies’ missions.

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
CNRS/Huma-Num	Clara Petitfils Suzanne Dumouchel Nicolas Larrousse Edward J. Gray	clara.petitfils@huma-num.fr suzanne.dumouchel@huma-num.fr nicolas.larrousse@huma-num.fr edward.gray@huma-num.fr
DARIAH	Laure Barbot Arnaud Roi	laure.barbot@dariah.eu arnaud.roi@dariah.eu
DARIAH/OEAW	Matej Ďurčo Klaus Illmayer	Matej.Durco@oeaw.ac.at Klaus.Illmayer@oeaw.ac.at
DARIAH/UGOE	Stefan Buddenbohm	sbudden@gwdg.de
PSNC	Tomasz Parkola	tparkola@man.poznan.pl

Executive Summary

This report aims at describing the governance model for the SSH Open Marketplace, especially in the perspective of its sustainability. A well-thought governance model is required to sustain the various components of this SSH discovery portal: from its technical development and ongoing future maintenance (aggregation and ingestion pipelines, integration of new resources, curation, and editorial components) to its more strategic design through the definition of governing bodies and roles.

The guidelines presented in this report need to be read and understood as a first version of the SSH Open Marketplace sustainability scheme that can be updated throughout the project's evolution and especially the Marketplace's development.

This deliverable is a result of the work carried out as part of SSHOC Task 7.4 - "Governance: Population, Curation & Sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace", itself embedded in WP7 - "Creating the SSH Open Marketplace" of the SSHOC project. It supports the creation of the SSH Open Marketplace: a discovery portal crafted for the SSH research community, offering contextualised solutions to diverse research enquiries, at every step of a researcher's data life cycle.

This deliverable has considered the work done under WP8, especially Task 8.1 "Governance & Sustainability" (lead CLARIN ERIC) handling the overall governance of the SSHOC project, and the consultation processes conducted among the SSHOC Scientific and Project Management Boards.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACDH-CH	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DH	Digital Humanities
CC	Contributors Community
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DiRT	Digital Research Tools
EB	Editorial Board
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESS	European Social Survey
GB	Governing Board
NFDI	National research data infrastructure
OBERRED	Open Badge Ecosystem for the Recognition of Skills in Research Data Management & Sharing
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
PM	person-month
RfII	German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
TAPoR	Text Analysis Portal for Research
TRIPLE	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked interdisciplinary Exploration
TRL	Technical Readiness Level

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Introduction

The deliverable’s context of publication

This deliverable is generated as part of the work carried out in Task 7.4 - “Governance: Population, Curation & Sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace”, itself embedded in WP7 - “Creating the SSH Open Marketplace” of the SSHOC project. It consequently supports the creation of the SSH Open Marketplace. The Marketplace is a discovery portal for SSH resources, namely: tools/services, training materials, workflows, datasets, and publications. Because it focuses on SSH resources, this portal is naturally intended for the SSH research community to which it expects to offer enrichment of research methods through a threefold added value: **contextualisation**, **curation**, and **community**. Indeed, the SSH Open Marketplace offers “contextualised” resources to diverse research enquiries, at every step of the life cycle of a research data set. Those resources (e.g., a tool or service) are therefore linked to other potentially useful resources (e.g., a training material or a publication). This contextualisation will therefore foster serendipity in digital methods. More important is that this very contextualisation is made possible through a community-oriented approach of the curation process. In other words, it is based on the community’s participation in the curation process (understood as metadata generation and enrichment). The SSH Open Marketplace thus carries a unique community- and user-oriented mission: it is crafted not only for the users but also by the users themselves.

What is the SSH Open Marketplace?	What it is not?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a discovery portal, to foster serendipity in digital methods - an aggregator of useful and well curated resources - a catalogue, contextualising resources - an opportunity for “other research outputs” than services to be visible in the EOSC - a contribution to the EOSC Exchange seen as one of the main entry points for the SSH cluster in the EOSC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - not a repository. Nothing is hosted in the SSH Open Marketplace. Workflow content type can be hosted, but this is an exception - not a data catalogue. The goal is not to collect all the SSH datasets, but selected datasets are indexed to support the contextualisation (dataset mentioned in a publication or used in a training material for example). - not a commercial Marketplace. There is nothing to sell in the SSH Open Marketplace. Commercial software/services can be referenced.

Table 1: A Value Proposition for the SSH Open Marketplace

This report describes the governance model for this SSH Open Marketplace, especially in the perspective of its sustainability.

The SSH Open Marketplace is part of a rich environment: the DARIAH strategic plan¹ and services discussion², the SSHOC project services (and SSH RI service offers in general) and the EOSC services. The SSHOC project dimension is particularly relevant for the Marketplace's governance: first through all its involved partners, including the SSH ERICs, other SSH institutions and national research infrastructures and the community this platform envisages to reach (all SSH disciplines and professions). Secondly, through the EOSC landscape, since SSHOC represents its SSH cluster. Because of this very European ecosystem and initiative, the SSH Open Marketplace understandably conveys a strategic role for the use and visibility of SSH resources. It embodies one of the key SSH entry points to the EOSC. These different ecosystems' levels (DARIAH, SSHOC, EOSC) are here considered and addressed by combining the need for both high-level governance and operational governance.

The drafting of D7.5 governance guidelines lead to consider several elements (1) the development work, including for the SSH Open Marketplace, will still be ongoing until the end of the SSHOC project (April 2022) and (2) the difficulty to forecast the future and financing of digital services and tools after the end of a Horizon 2020 project. Furthermore, the ongoing work of the SSHOC Scientific Board (WP1) for a SSHOC Exploitation Plan, and Task 8.1 "Governance & sustainability" that is working on "appropriate governance model for the SSH part of the EOSC"³ are also considered as part of this context and will contribute to clarify the SSH part of the EOSC landscape in which the SSH Open Marketplace is positioned. Because the overall context of the SSH Open Marketplace is still very much under development, those guidelines will thus remain generic: they need to be read and understood as a first version of the SSH Open Marketplace sustainability scheme. This governance model should be adapted throughout the project's evolution through T7.4.

The chosen approach

To meet all these requirements, the T7.4 team provides a well-balanced approach to the sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace. More precisely, the strategic design, the curation components and the community aspects of the discovery portal are carefully considered. Indeed, as already highlighted by previous work, the "directory paradox"⁴ is a well-known limit of collaborative and community-led

¹ DARIAH Strategic Plan 2019-2026: https://www.dariah.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Strategic-Plan_2019-2026.pdf [13.09.2021]

² see Barbot, Laure, Roi, Arnaud, Scharnhorst, Andrea, Durco, Matej, Fischer, Frank, Kalman, Tibor, ... Toth-Czifra, Erzsebet. (2021, March 19). Towards a concise DARIAH service strategy: 2020 Reflections - White Paper. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621287> [23.06.2021]

³ SSHOC Grant Agreement, Task 8.1 description

⁴ See for example, Dombrowski, Rockwell, "The Directory Paradox". Forthcoming in Debates in Digital Humanities: Institutions, Infrastructures at the Interstices. Univ. of Minnesota Press. Eds. Anne McGrail et al. See also "Who needs tool directories? A forum on sustaining discovery portals large and small" Forum submitted for DH2020 Conference: <https://dh2020directoriesforum.hcommons.org/> [10.09.2021].

registries - at least in the Digital Humanities context - and the mechanisms allowing the SSH Open Marketplace to increase discoverability and accessibility of up-to-date content and to support users' direct contributions in the long-run were at the heart of the work conducted by T7.4.

Furthermore, the “last mile” challenge for community engagement is exactly where Research Infrastructures and their services, such as the SSH Open Marketplace, intend to position themselves. The following citation illustrates how an appropriate user-oriented approach, embedded in an efficient curation workflow and supported by the right mechanisms to engage users can make the difference: “There is a significant disconnect between the rates of technological progress in the development of research e-infrastructures and uptake by researchers. To mitigate this risk, it is imperative that e-infrastructure services are accessible through consistent easy-to-use interfaces, which provide integrated and ubiquitous access. These interfaces should have the same simplicity and maturity as the consumer-oriented Web applications we are already familiar with. Intuitive user interface experience, seamless data ingestion, and collaboration capabilities are among the features that could empower users to better engage with provided services.”⁵

That is why, to foster the community-oriented approach of the SSHOC project and of the SSH Open Marketplace, it was chosen that the SSH community itself could take part as “Contributors” in this curation process, alongside dedicated “Moderators”. Therefore, the construction of this curation process and workflow naturally relies on both this D7.5 *Governance* deliverable but also D7.4 *Marketplace – Data population & curation* (due for M36).

In order to avoid unnecessary repetition and to guarantee the relevance of the governance-related curation content, this deliverable will only approach the strategic governance and design of the SSH Open Marketplace through two decisive entities: the Governing board and the Contributors' community. The in-depth study of the curation process and its roles are, logically, left for D7.4 *Marketplace – Data population and curation*.

⁵ Koureas D, Arvanitidis C, Belbin L, Berendsohn W, Damgaard C, Groom Q, Güntsch A, Hagedorn G, Hardisty A, Hobern D, Marcer A, Mietchen D, Morse D, Obst M, Penev L, Pettersson L, Sierra S, Smith V, Vos R (2016) Community engagement: The ‘last mile’ challenge for European research e-infrastructures. *Research Ideas and Outcomes* 2: e9933. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.2.e9933> [13.09.2021]

First thoughts on the Governance scheme

Basis of the governance model

As explained above, T7.4 team had to consider a rather rich context during its work: the alignment with the technical development of the Marketplace and its curation, the potential involvement of SSHOC stakeholders - especially ERICs - and the EOSC initiative, including other complementary SSH projects, such as TRIPLE⁶. To best apprehend this, a dedicated Task Force Governance was established to exchange with interested partners.

Firstly, the level of SSHOC partners' involvement in this future governance had to be settled. The Task Force suggested three options (governance schemes), later discussed, and decided by the SSHOC Scientific Board⁷: 1/ a single DARIAH ERIC governance, 2/ a shared governance at the level of national research infrastructures and 3/ a shared governance between SSH ERICs. The latter was welcomed by the SSHOC Scientific Board. This model opted for a shared governance between the ERICs involved in the SSHOC project⁸, with a cooperation foreseen for at least the first year after the end of the SSHOC Project. In this perspective, the SSH Open Marketplace could pave the way for a more reinforced and structured collaboration between the ERICs, especially in terms of service provision.

Selecting this latter option was seen as a first step towards a governance model which answers to the needs and the willingness of organisations to be involved in the SSH Open Marketplace. Nevertheless, all other options remain open and even a mixed model of the shared governance scheme can be seen as a major option. Indeed, one of the challenges for SSHOC services is to suggest mechanisms to ensure the sustainability of European thematic services provision in an EOSC environment in which the roles and responsibilities of national and thematic/disciplinary layers or angles are not yet stabilised⁹.

In addition to identifying governance options, an analysis was conducted to identify suitable models for governance and governing bodies that could implement the SSH Open Marketplace. Several types of

⁶ TRIPLE project website: <https://www.gotriple.eu/> [08.06.2021]

⁷ As stated in the SSHOC Grant Agreement, the Scientific Board, or so-called 1st-Tier, is chaired by the Coordinator of the project, CESSDA ERIC, and includes the representatives of the 1st ring decision-making group (heads of key partners in the project).

⁸ Namely CESSDA ERIC, CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, ESS ERIC and SHARE ERIC.

⁹ Just like European organizations per se, the EOSC is naturally organized along national nodes, in terms of governance, services to federate, stakeholder groups etc. However, the thematic/disciplinary clusters, organizations of actors and services, forms another, just as fundamental layer in the EOSC landscape, serving as primary hubs of scientific innovation. A clarification of how these two cross-cutting angles are positioned in relation to each other in terms of respective roles and responsibilities remains to be thematised and addressed by the EOSC stakeholders and executive bodies.

bodies were considered for the Marketplace's sustainability and three entities were presented and adopted by the SSHOC Scientific Board in early 2019. This model includes three entities:

- Governing Board (GB): committed to the development and strategic sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace as its ultimate decision-making authority;
- Editorial Board (EB): dedicated to the Marketplace editorial work and composed of "Moderators" and "Administrators";
- Contributors Community (CC): dedicated to community participation in the curation process and composed of "Contributors" (however not a body properly speaking).

What is guiding the rationale behind the governance of the SSH Open Marketplace is the fundamental need to ensure that the service built will be sustained and maintained in the long run¹⁰. In other terms, what the T7.4 team investigated is the idea of a "business model" as it was described in a recent discussion paper from the German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures (RfII)¹¹: *"The term "business model" is used here in the not-for-profit sense, with a focus on sustainability and resource conservation, the distribution of roles and responsibilities, and the rights and obligations of data or service providers."*

Rationale behind the SSH Open Marketplace's Governance

Due to the specificity of the SSH Open Marketplace, Governance and Curation aspects are intertwined and complementary. The SSH Open Marketplace aims to offer contextualised resources to the SSH research community. This contextualisation itself relies on the quality of the content displayed and therefore on the discovery portal's data population and curation.

Those aspects undoubtedly require capable bodies and fundings (human capacity) to take on this editorial mission. That is where the curation and the governance of the SSH Open Marketplace find themselves very much intertwined. Although very much liaised and complementary, a clear distinction however needs to be made here, for the sake of the reader's clarity. The reader won't find here the details of this curation component: whether through the curation criteria and process or the editorial guidelines, since a dedicated deliverable D7.4 *Marketplace – Data population & curation* (due for December 31st, 2021,

¹⁰ Aligned with CENDARI project recommendations in terms of sustainability - see Jennifer Edmond and Francesca Morselli, Sustainability of Digital Humanities Projects as a Publication and Documentation Challenge, *Journal of Documentation*, 76, 2, 2020 -, at least a 5-year plan after the end of the SSHOC project should be ensured by the SSH Open Marketplace sustainability plan. Nevertheless, considering ERICs' involvement and the EOSC context, a longer period (10 years) has been chosen to develop the costs estimation.

¹¹ RfII – German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures: Building Sustainable Data Services. RfII Discussion Paper on the Enhancement of Research Data Infrastructures, Göttingen 2020 <http://www.rfii.de/download/rfii-discussion-paper-on-the-enhancement-of-research-data-infrastructures-september-2020/> [accessed 17.12.2020]

or M36) is intended for that. What is instead suggested here, is to present the curation effort through its definition in the broader governance scheme.

The “curation” is defined as the governance of all curation, both technical and editorial-related, roles and missions of the SSH Open Marketplace. Assuming that each governing entity plays its part into the curation process, two of them can be particularly noted: the Editorial Board and the Contributors Community. For this later one, the approach is particularly complex: based on a community of users or “Contributors”, the challenge is here to continuously encourage and support participation. Therefore, the means for community involvement should be inclusive and dynamic to successfully foster spontaneous contributions to the curation process.

The success of those curation-related individual entities will of course depend heavily on Governance, which can be defined as the upper level of governance including all defined structural organisations, missions, and rules necessary to the sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace. Here, one can observe that both levels cannot go without the other one and that both equally impact one another. The objective for this deliverable will be to determine the correct equilibrium between both.

The Governing bodies

This section presents the SSH Open Marketplace's main governing bodies through the Governing Board and the Editorial Board. This section must be read as a first version: their strategic design will indeed be further discussed by the SSHOC Scientific Board. This work could also be adjusted, based on the outcome of WP8 work.

This section carries a strategic perspective regarding the SSH Open Marketplace. As described above, Governance includes all defined structural organisations, missions and rules realising the sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace. Although key to the success of the discovery portal management, the Governance section of this deliverable should not be too constraining for future development as the Marketplace is still being under development until the end of the SSHOC project. To fully consider this construction in the long run, flexibility and adaptability will be key in the reading and later implementation of this section.

As stated in the first part, the Governance builds on two bodies: the Governing Board and the Editorial Board. In addition, the Contributors Community counts as an effort to ensure the service uptake and to gather the user community around the curation effort.

The Governing Board

The Governing Board is committed to support the sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace. It acts as its ultimate decision-making authority. Since the SSH Open Marketplace is still under construction, further development could modify and/or add up more responsibilities to this body.

MISSIONS

The Governing Board defines the Marketplace strategic policy with regards to scientific, technical, and managerial matters.

With regards to scientific matters:

- The Governing Board defines and decides on the scientific orientation of the Marketplace. The scientific orientation is defined here as the orientation chosen to foster the offer and effectiveness with regards to SSH research's needs and challenges.
- The scientific orientation's decisions, when related to core editorial aspects, are taken alongside the Editorial Board, especially when those relate to editorial choices.
- Any recommendation or demand for action from the Editorial Board, regarding editorial policies (addition, modification, deletion) shall be approved by the Governing Board.
- In the light of the Marketplace strategic scientific orientation, the Governing Board should work to ensure the best alignment conceivable between the EOSC and the SSH Open Marketplace. For this aim, the body has to maintain contact with relevant actors from SSHOC and EOSC.

With regards to technical matters:

- The Governing Board approves the decisions of the Editorial Board. If any conflict arises from different approaches, then the Governing Board decides.
- Any recommendation or demand for action from the Editorial Board, editing the technical policy (addition, modification, deletion) shall be approved by the Governing Board.

With regards to managerial matters:

- The Governing Board defines the annual budget and the work plan - **The SSH Open Marketplace Strategic work plan** - which is regularly updated to pursue the agile methodology adopted so far for the implementation of the Marketplace.
- Any recommendation or demand for action from the Editorial Board, editing the strategic orientation (addition, modification, deletion) shall be approved by the Governing Board.
- The above-mentioned administrative components should be made after consulting the Editorial Board, but also when deemed necessary, the Contributors Community, to understand their needs and expectations.
- The above-mentioned administrative components should be agreed based on the mechanism for decision taking for decision taking suggested below.
- The Governing Board oversees and directs the work undertaken in the other body, the Editorial Board, but also in the Contributors Community.

COMPOSITION

The Governing Board is composed of representatives of the contributing partner ERICs. “Contributing partners” can be defined as partners that financially contribute to the sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace.

This representation will be organised as follow:

- The Governing Board is composed of one representative per ERIC, independently from each contribution. The body will therefore count five members - at least for the first year after the SSHOC project’s end.
- Each contributing ERIC appoints its own representative for the Marketplace’s Governing Board.
- This body should gather twice a year. This pace should be tested during the first year of this governance scheme’s implementation. Later, if a different scheduling is required and preferred by representatives, another model will be adopted.

The decision-making process will be organised as follow:

- As the group is rather small, consensus should be the first decision-making process adopted.
- If the consensus is not reached, then a voting system is required, and a fair and well-balanced process should be ensured. The following mechanism is therefore suggested:

- To consider the possibility that an ERIC could contribute more than others, a voting based on the financial contribution's proportionality can be considered.
- However, to avoid a potential "voting monopoly" based solely on the financial weight, the voting should, in addition, gather at least the majority of representatives (thus three out of five members).
- The decision-making process is agreed in the agreement signed by the GB members and should be modified by unanimity.

RELATIONS TO OTHER BODIES

As described above, the Governing Board determines the Marketplace's strategic orientation and policies on scientific, technical, and managerial matters. Regarding all three fields, whether the consensus or the proportionality voting mechanism is chosen as the decision-making process the Governing Board shall always consult the other body and take its recommendations into account. For instance, the Editorial Board, involved in the daily operation of the Marketplace will be able to provide frequent and operational-related inputs to the Governing Board. It should also consider the Contributors Community's needs, challenges, and expectations.

The Editorial Board

The Editorial board of the SSH Open Marketplace forms as the central coordinating board for the daily operation of the service. It contributes to the formulation of the Marketplace's editorial policy, based on its recommendations, alongside the Governing Board, based, among others, on its observation of the Contributors Community. The Editorial Board acts under the supervision of the Governing Board. Its core priority remains the implementation of the Governing Board's strategic orientation relating to its activities (technical, editorial, and curation-related matters).

MISSIONS

The Editorial Board is in charge of the Marketplace's day-to-day operation of service. It ensures this regular maintenance through several scopes: the technical running of operation, the effectiveness of the curation process and the editorial policy's successful implementation.

With regards to the technical maintenance of operation:

- The Editorial Board ensures the day-to-day technical maintenance of operation of the SSH Open Marketplace. When deemed necessary, it can refer to the Governing Board.
- The Editorial Board is responsible for new data sources ingestion in the Marketplace/ harvesting third party sources.

With regards to the curation process and editorial policy implementation:

- Following the defined Editorial Guidelines (see deliverable D7.4), the Editorial Board's members work on the three missions:

- Create or update items of the Marketplace.
- Review a recent addition/ingestion to the portal, including automatic checks.
- Review Contributors' contributions and suggested items (whether addition or modification of items): the Moderator audits, decides and implements the suggested enhancements or enrichments of the item. If this process leads to new insights or demand for action, it will be discussed in the Editorial Board and later with the Governing Board if the matter requires a strategic decision.
- This activity includes a coordination effort from the Editorial Board with the curation-related community (Contributors Community).
- This body is the contact point with regards to community engagement in the curation process (Contributors Community) and for general users of the Marketplace.

Although working primarily on the implementation of the Governing board's strategic orientation, the Editorial Board can formulate recommendations or demand action on specific matters to the Governing Board when required. The Editorial Board can therefore contribute to the strategic orientation.

COMPOSITION

The Editorial Board is mainly composed of experts: the Moderators and Administrators of the SSH Open Marketplace. They have all rights with regard to editing the content and filtering the "noisy input" from the Contributors or from harvesting third party sources.

As mentioned above, *D7.4 Marketplace - Data population and curation* is expected for the end of 2021: a thorough description of the curation-related roles will then be provided in this expected deliverable. This section will thus only provide a generic overview - that could be up to modifications considering that the curation components are still under development.

With regards to Moderators¹² and Administrators¹³ organisation's mode:

- The Editorial Board is managed by one Coordinator: The Chief moderator. They are recruited (full-time or half-time) by the Governing Board (ERICs). The Coordinator oversees both the Editorial Board and the Contributors Community.
- Moderators are appointed by the Governing Board, chosen among the ERICs' community (in-kind contribution for the GB members) or beyond, based on their expertise and work experience. Moderators' work is expected to be funded by in-kind contributions but could also be based on a voluntary contribution.
- Moderators cannot be a representative from the Governing Board at the same time.

¹² A SSH Open Marketplace Moderator is defined as a member of a group of moderators that is managed by a designated Coordinator. Moderators are a subset of the members of the SSH Open Marketplace's Editorial Board.

¹³ A SSH Open Marketplace Administrator is defined as a member whose role is to maintain the content of the Marketplace, as they can be moderators, and also to ensure the overall technical maintenance of the Marketplace. Administrators work in close collaboration with Moderators.

The ideal size for the Editorial Board is around fifteen members, with a strict minimum of six (assigned by the ERICs and the Coordinator) and an operational maximum of around thirty, after which coordination becomes difficult to manage. T7.4 team foresees that, to grow from the six “statutory” members that the ERICs will appoint, a call for interest among the SSHOC communities and beyond should be organised before the end of the project. Indeed, the first members of the Editorial Board, after consultation with the Governing Board, should aim at stabilising the team before April 2022.

RELATIONS TO OTHER BODIES

Following the consensus-based approach of the governance scheme and of the links between each body, the Editorial Board maintains a close collaboration with both the Governing Board and the Contributors Community, especially in the light of its editorial/curation-related activities - central for the Marketplace and its governance.

First, with regards to the Governing Board:

- The Editorial Board is consulted for any relevant decisions and strategic orientations on scientific, technical, and managerial matters prepared by the Governing Board.
- The other way around, the Editorial Board can, whenever it deems necessary, raise awareness, provide recommendations, or demand action to the Governing Board which decides to approve those. However, as the Governing Board remains the ultimate authority of the Marketplace, the Editorial Board cannot give instructions.
- When providing recommendations on technical or curation and editorial-related issues, the Editorial Board can suggest new strategic orientation or the reformulation or deletion of existing ones.

Secondly, with regards to the Contributors Community:

- The Editorial Board receives and takes into account feedback formulated by the Contributors’ Community.
- The Editorial Board acts as the contact point of this community.

The Contributors Community

How can the SSH Open Marketplace try to overcome the “directory paradox”¹⁴? Thanks to previous experiences - such as Bamboo DiRT¹⁵ -, we know that the crowdsourced directory maintenance is a challenge per se. In fact, in the north American context, the two longest-running DH tool directories (TAPoR¹⁶ and DH Toychest¹⁷) are led by individuals supported by their home institution for the hosting and technical maintenance and don’t rely on community input to update their content¹⁸. The SSH Open Marketplace aims to address the directory paradox through a twofold approach: a shared governance model in the EOSC environment and a coordination of the collective efforts needed to ensure the content maintenance. While the shared governance has been detailed in the previous sections, this section describes the approach and the different mechanisms envisioned to involve research communities in the continuous curation model of the SSH Open Marketplace.

Users’ profile

Let’s first clarify what is/will be the SSH Open Marketplace community. Based on the SSHOC stakeholder landscape analysis of the Community Engagement Strategy designed by WP6¹⁹ and the stakeholder categories identified there, it should be noted that targeted users of the SSH Open Marketplace belong mainly to three categories - researchers, research libraries and archives, universities and research performing organisations - but other stakeholders may have an interest as well:

Stakeholder category	Main areas of interest towards the SSH Open Marketplace
Researchers, scholars, students	Searching for resources useful to their individual research or teaching undertakings; general search interest; peer group orientation (e.g. current trends in DH)
Research libraries and archives	Identification of possible linkages of marketplace’ resources with their holdings to improve FAIR use of their collections;

¹⁴ See p.8, footnote 4 for the details of this concept.

¹⁵ Quinn Dombrowski, What Ever Happened to Project Bamboo?, *Literary and Linguistic Computing*, Volume 29, Issue 3, September 2014, Pages 326–339, <https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/fqu026> [13.09.2021]

¹⁶ TAPoR website: <http://tapor.ca/home> [13.09.2021]

¹⁷ DH Toychest website: <http://dhresourcesforprojectbuilding.pbworks.com/w/page/69244243/FrontPage> [13.09.2021]

¹⁸ “The DH Toychest and TAPoR (...) as long-running directory projects led by individual, tenured faculty members that have attained a greater level of stability as a consequence of their directors’ positions but face similar [sustainability] challenges over a longer timeframe.” in “The Directory Paradox”. Forthcoming in *Debates in Digital Humanities: Institutions, Infrastructures at the Interstices*. Univ. of Minnesota Press. Eds. Anne McGrail et al.

¹⁹ Torma, Martina, Kalaitzi, Vasso, Vipavc Brvar, Irena, Fišer, Darja, Pahor de Maiti, Kristina, Petitfils, Clara, ... Willems, Marieke. (2019). SSHOC D6.1 Community Engagement Strategy (Version v1.0). Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592243>, [09.02.2021]

	inspiration for an improved provision of their collections
Providers of resources (such as tools or tutorials)	Improved visibility and uptake of their resources; integration of individual resources into a larger context (e.g., linking up of a tool with a tutorial)
Policy makers and funders	Orientation on the current landscape of research practices in the SSH; identification of gaps in the current offer; inspiration on trends or upcoming topics, which should be considered by either the policy or the funding strategy
Research infrastructure contexts	Identification of possible cooperation and synergies (e.g., common infrastructure at national level (NFDI ²⁰ in the German context for example, or disciplinary related resources in the EOSC portal)

Table 2: User groups and their interests in the SSH Open Marketplace

Furthermore, as highlighted in D6.1, SSHOC partners “already represent a big part of the SSH community” which is why the engagement strategy of the whole project builds “on existing networks, channels and tools”. The same goes for the SSH Open Marketplace, as one of the services developed in SSHOC, first users and communities involved are either affiliated to project partners or familiar with the Research Infrastructures communities. This is a good starting point, but it is not enough in the long term. Strategies for opening up the service to other communities are considered and the initial users can be seen as a lever or a first step in building a wider user community.

Building the SSH Open Marketplace users’ community can be seen as a continuation of the User-Centered Approach adopted since the beginning of the project. Interviews and user stories have supported the user requirements process²¹. A Public Consultation Platform, some “guerilla interviews” and live consultations of users have also been conducted over the course of 2020²². Finally, as of February 2020, 133 testers registered to the Marketplace testers mailing list, representing the first circle of users. Out of those testers we were able to highlight some features of these future users. They mainly represent the social sciences (53 testers declared Sociology as a discipline to which they are “affiliated”) and have either a librarian/data stewardship or a researcher profile. We also count a significant share of other disciplines: humanities and linguistics but also cultural heritage and museology.

²⁰ National Research Data Infrastructure description:

https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/programmes/nfdi/index.html [13.09.2021]

²¹ Laure Barbot, Yoan Moranville, Frank Fischer, Clara Petitfils, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, ... Sotiris Karampatakis. (2019). SSHOC D7.1 System Specification - SSH Open Marketplace (Version 1.0). Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3547648> [08.06.2021]

²² See Laure Barbot, Frank Fischer, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Alexander König, Dieter Van Uytvanck, & Nicolas Larrousse. (2020). MS.43 -Marketplace - beta release (Version 1.0). Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4785193> [15.07.2021]

From users to contributors: what kind of model to foster engagement?

While an anonymous user is considered as a member of the community, a contributor is a user who logs into the Marketplace to enrich existing records in the directory or create new ones. This level of involvement - suggesting a contribution - has been designed to be user-friendly and as easy and quick as possible. The fact that most of the contributions expected concerns metadata and not data themselves and that the disciplines perimeter covers a large SSH spectrum, are challenges to connect to specific communities of practices, but this is a rather common problematic in the Research Infrastructures environment, and the SSH Open Marketplace can surely build on previous experiences to find the best model to implement to foster engagement. Two examples can be highlighted here to get a better sense of what is foreseen for the Marketplace:

- In the *Digital Humanities Course Registry* - a common service between CLARIN and DARIAH - national moderators are acting as local ambassadors and ensure efficient and distributed content maintenance. This service is also supported by an eponymous Working Group.²³ Regular community activities - supported via the DARIAH Funding Theme or by the service provider institution - provide the necessary framework for usability and uptake of the service. For example, a hackathon was organised by ACDH-CH in 2020²⁴ and participants were invited to play with the service API to suggest new data visualisations.
- The *Standardization Survival Kit* developed within the former PARTHENOS project also presents an interesting way to engage with Humanities and Cultural Heritage communities. Thanks to project funding, several *datathons* have been organised, in order to create new content (research scenarios) for the platform²⁵. This content management and maintenance is ensured by the DARIAH Working Group Guidelines and Standards.

Based on these non-exhaustive examples, several key aspects to engage contributors with the SSH Open Marketplace can be noted. Contributors are active users of the service (positioned, in terms of engagement between anonymous users and moderators) and their engagement needs to be regularly supported by dedicated activities (i.e., *hackathons*, *datathons*). The SSH Open Marketplace does not aim at creating a community as such but should rely on existing working groups, research, and infrastructure networks to ensure the uptake of the service. The editorial board has a key role to play in terms of community management and engagement.

²³ DH Course Registry Working Group,
<https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups/dh-course-registry/>, [11.02.2021]

²⁴ ACDH-CH hackathon 2020,
<https://www.oeaw.ac.at/acdh/detail/event/acdh-ch-open-data-virtual-hackathon-round-two/>, [11.02.2021]

²⁵ See this summary of SSK datathons, <https://www.dariah.eu/2020/07/16/dariah-theme-2018-2019-awareness-understanding-and-having-fun-fostering-communities-around-the-standardization-survival-kit/>, [11.02.2021]

Incentives and rewards

The SSH Open Marketplace has to find a path between pure volunteer work of its contributors and crowd-based maintenance of content. Indeed, the ethics of planning for volunteering work and the question of what rewards and incentives to provide are a rising and ongoing discussion in the digital humanities.²⁶ What kind of incentives can be envisioned for users to contribute to the SSH Open Marketplace content improvement? Based on the feedback from the testers community, diverse trends and motivations have been identified. Some contributors would be interested in seeing their own work referenced in the platform, some others would consider their contributions as an opportunity to step into the world of SSH infrastructures when others would consider their contribution as part of their academic interests and duties. Beyond these individual motivations - that could be better investigated thanks to advanced user stories - the basic approach to incentivise and reward contributions can be described as follows:

- The first and basic step to ensure that contributions are recognised consists of acknowledging and citing every contributor in the SSH Open Marketplace. Following the recommendations of SSHOC WP3 - T3.4 Making Data Findable by being Citable - a `cite-as` property has been implemented in the SSH Open Marketplace, which will give a link to the Marketplace Entry and include the names of Contributors to the entry. This effort, by automatically gathering contributors' names, eases the citation process and increases the potential benefits for Contributors in terms of academic credit.²⁷
- The second dimension, developed to incite contributions, follows successful approaches implemented by other services mentioned above: cash prizes or travel grants as rewards for specific community involvement activities. This requires a financial investment from the Governing Board members, as outlined below.
- Another approach that was suggested but not investigated in-depth is the possibility to implement Open Badges - such as the ones developed for example within the Open Badge Ecosystem for the Recognition of Skills in Research Data Management & Sharing (OBERRED) project²⁸

²⁶ Adam Crymble, *Technology and the Historian: Transformations in the Digital Age* (Chicago: University of Illinois Press, 2021), 64-72 and Simon Burrows and Glenn Roe, eds., *Digitizing Enlightenment: Digital Humanities and the Transformation of Eighteenth-Century Studies* (Liverpool: Liverpool University Press), notably Sean Takats, "Conclusion: Beyond Digitizing Enlightenment."

²⁷ Despite the fact that these kinds of academic activities are not (yet) direct assets for an academic career, the SSH Open Marketplace aims at contributing to the cultural change that is slowly happening in taking into account other research outputs than publications. Citations in the SSH Open Marketplace will be further described in D7.4, let us just highlight here the distinction between contributors of the SSH Open Marketplace and actors/creators of a resource referenced in the Marketplace. Obviously, the goal of a discovery portal is to increase the visibility of the resources referenced - so to increase the findability of research outputs created by scholars - but we also believe that contributions to the Marketplace curation are a scholarly activity that deserves its own credit.

²⁸ See OBERRED project website: <https://oberred.eu/> [08.06.2021]

- Finally, a possibility to join the Editorial Board for very active and interested contributors is also foreseen as a useful and concrete incentive. Indeed, by opening these positions to members of the community, the SSH Open Marketplace team hopes to capture the best of the enthusiasm and knowledge of the different communities of practice and put that to the benefit of the SSH Open Marketplace, while rewarding people involved in return.

Nevertheless, and as discussed during one of the consultation sessions in 2020²⁹, all the rewards and incentives possible should not lead to competition between actors. The Editorial Board of the SSH Open Marketplace, following the Governing Board orientations, will be in charge of implementing and monitoring the users' community involvement and will be free to suggest new methods to foster the uptake of the service. Furthermore, Task 7.4 members expect that the outputs of the two EOSC Task Forces, "Researcher Engagement and Adoption" and "Research Careers, Recognition and Credit" will support the decisions of the Governing Board.

²⁹ See DARIAH public consultation of the SSH Open Marketplace, <https://www.dariah.eu/2020/08/07/dariah-public-consultation-of-the-ssh-open-marketplace/>, [11.02.2021]

Ensuring sustainability

As members of different entities, Contributors, Moderators and Administrators are involved in the governance and can ensure, with the Governing Board, that technical, scientific, and also financial decisions to sustain the service are taken on an informed basis.

To prepare the sustainability plan of the SSH Open Marketplace, different costs have been taken into account, especially linked to the Editorial Board which will represent the highest costs of the service. Existing services and previous experiences of the partners involved - at the national or European level - were also gathered and EOSC integration (inclusion criteria for onboarding³⁰ and current Resource Maturity Classification³¹) options were also taken into consideration to present the estimate below.

This section includes a twofold approach. First, cost estimation scenarios are provided, structured into categories and aligned with the entities and roles described above. Then, some recommendations to set up the financial and contractual framework needed to realise these scenarios are provided.

Cost estimation scenarios

Two scenarios are presented below:

1. The minimum scenario (or silver scenario) includes the strictly necessary funding needed to keep the service up and running after the end of the SSHOC project. In this scenario, people with the technical expertise would be available to fix bugs and implement security updates. In terms of content, 1-2 new data sources could be ingested every year³², and the moderators team could work towards a better data quality while supporting the organisation of 1-2 hands-on sessions or curation sprints per year to collect new content from the research community. A half-time chief moderator position is foreseen in this scenario. Thanks to this estimation, the SSH Open Marketplace could reach the TRL 8 - Production as defined by the EOSC Technology Readiness Levels.
2. The more ambitious scenario (or gold scenario) implies a stronger engagement of the three entities described above (regarding the funding, the management and maintenance), allowing to reach TRL 9 - Production³³ after one year. Costs listed in this more ambitious scenario would ensure not only the minimum viable service (cf. silver scenario), but:

³⁰ EOSC Provider Portal - Inclusion Criteria: <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-inclusion-criteria>; [10.08.2021]

³¹ EOSC Provider Portal - Resource Maturity Classification: <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-resource-maturity-classification>; [10.08.2021]

³² See D7.3 Marketplace – Interoperability for more details about the external sources ingested during the project lifetime and the recommendations for future data ingests.

³³ Especially, customer feedback would be gathered and documented, as required by the EOSC Resource Maturity Classification.

- a. a full-time chief moderator position
- b. a better data population & quality (i.e., 3-4 external sources ingestion, an extended Editorial Team and 3-4 hands-on sessions with the users),
- c. which is a guarantee of a better uptake of the service (i.e., more users).
- d. With the possibility to add functionalities and not only regular refactoring, a better alignment with the future EOSC inclusion criteria for thematic services could be ensured.

SSHOC Deliverable 7.3 “Marketplace interoperability” and D7.4 “Marketplace - Data Population & curation” are each providing more details on sources selection for the first data population ingested during the SSHOC project lifetime and on the generic entry requirements as well as the quality criteria to be considered to be added in the SSH Open Marketplace. Prioritisation and selection of the future data sources, considering the limited resources to process these sources after the end of the project, is a key element. Findings of these deliverables can be summarised as follows:

- a distinction between mass & manual ingestion is established and different entry requirements have to be met depending on the ingestion type
- Scientific, Technical, Contextualization and Legal/Ethical requirements are defined by the SSH Open Marketplace Editorial Guidelines
- Quality criteria to ensure at the entry and/or improve data already ingested are defined in the Editorial Guidelines as well.

For both scenarios, cost estimations consist of three main categories:

1. Operational costs: includes the costs for hardware, technical maintenance, constant operation of the service on a daily basis and the refactoring and new developments that will be needed in the course of the next 10 years.
2. Content costs: includes all costs related to the intellectual maintenance of the service, curation related costs, community involvement and dissemination efforts, such as training or recruiting of moderators.
3. Governing costs: includes costs related to the governance and institutional outreach needed for the service.

The person-month (PM) rate used for the estimation is the following: 1PM = 6 000€. And a period of 10-years’ time has been chosen to calculate non-recurring costs (i.e., non-annual basis costs such as the regular refactoring and the potential new developments). Note that these estimations comprise the minimum costs; any investment above and beyond these estimations could only help to improve the SSH Open Marketplace quality and uptake.

<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Annual cost Silver scenario</i>	<i>Annual cost Gold scenario</i>
Operational costs		
Maintenance backend (Bug fixing and/or security updates for 3rd-party programming libraries)	26 000€	66 000€
Ingestion: aggregation pipeline		
Maintenance frontend		
Hosting infrastructure		
Regular refactoring (4 refactorings in 10 years)		
New developments (2 projects in 10 years)	N/A	
Content costs		
Moderators' activities (curation tasks) and contributors' coordination (community management).	70 000€	137 000€
Rewards and incentives: travel grant for annual events/conferences & cash prizes for online events (editathon/hackathon).		
Governing costs		
Outreach costs (travel costs, conference fees to ensure Marketplace representation)	2 000€	3 000€
Governing Board participation		
Total	98 000 €	206 000 €

Table 3: Cost estimations for the SSH Open Marketplace

Contractual framework & funding for the SSH Open Marketplace

Based on the cost estimations presented above, several precisions and conceptual distinctions are added below to elaborate on the potential funding framework, precise the expected nature of the contributions, provide some examples of what it could look like for contributing partners and which contractual framework could be set up to ensure the SSH Open Marketplace sustainability.

First, **different sources of funding** can be envisioned and intertwined. A distinction between cash and in-kind contributions can be useful here³⁴. While the Governing participation or the moderators' activities could be provided by the Governing members as in-kind contributions, cash contributions would be needed to cover, for example, the outreach costs or to offer incentives to create additional content. Moreover, with a 10-year sustainability plan, regular refactoring and new developments are expected. For this kind of cost, specific (and external) funding could be targeted under the responsibility of all the stakeholders involved in the maintenance of the SSH Open Marketplace.

Future EOSC-related projects, and especially SSH- or cluster-oriented, should be monitored for that matter. But national or local financial support (e.g., grants) could also be considered to foster the development of the SSH Open Marketplace.

Finally, the ERICs could decide to set aside each year some funds to ensure a minimal amount of investment over the years. Based on the last discussion of the SSHOC Scientific Board, the following repartition is suggested below:

³⁴ Following a basic distinction, an in-kind contribution can be defined in its opposition to a cash contribution: it is a non-cash resource provided by a partner for the realisation of a common goal, in this case to sustain the SSH Open Marketplace. Because of the specific context in which this service is developed, the term “in-kind contribution” might cover different realities that this deliverable does not aim to detail, but a few pointers should nevertheless be mentioned. Both members of the EOSC Association and the Member States are expected to provide in-kind contributions to realise the EOSC - see the “Memorandum of Understanding for the Co-programmed European Partnership on the European Open Science Cloud”, <https://eosc.eu/documents> [13.07.2021]. Furthermore, in most of the ERICs, member countries are contributing the infrastructure via in-kind contributions as well, see the “In-kind Contributions in the Life of an ERIC” workshop presentations for an overview of the complexities of this topic for ERICs: <https://www.accelerate2020.eu/in-kind-contributions-in-the-life-of-an-eric-2/> [13.07.2021].

Nature/source of the funding	<i>In-kind contributions from GB members</i>	<i>Cash contributions from GB members</i>	<i>External funding or yearly savings</i>	<i>External funding</i>
Cost items	Moderators' activities Governing Board participation	Maintenance backend and frontend Aggregation pipeline Hosting Moderators' and contributors' coordination Rewards and incentives Outreach costs	Regular refactoring	New developments

Table 4: Potential sources of funding for the SSH Open Marketplace

The second important element to take into consideration is **how to share the costs among the Governing Board members**. As already mentioned at the beginning of this deliverable, the global agreement between SSHOC partners and other potential interested stakeholders to further develop the SSH branch of the EOSC after the SSHOC project is negotiated under WP1 and WP8, and will most probably lead to a light agreement, such as a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), that could mention an interest of the partners towards a coherent approach for an SSH service portfolio in the EOSC, but no details related to the management of a given service would be included. What is foreseen at this stage to ensure the SSH Open Marketplace sustainability plan, is the following contractual framework:

- A binding agreement between the members of the SSH Open Marketplace Governing Board will be signed. At the moment of writing, a template is being drafted by the T8.1 team. Based on the analysis conducted in this deliverable, the T7.4 team recommends the following provisions in this agreement. Similar settings could be followed for other EOSC services shared by ERICs:
 - Definition of the service, including its envisioned positioning in the (SSH) EOSC context
 - Scientific and technical policies as annexes describing the scientific scope and the technical building blocks of the service
 - Annual budget and its repartition between entities represented in the Governing Board
 - The SSH Open Marketplace Strategic work plan: an annual description of the objectives used to monitor the service
- A series of bilateral/multilateral agreements for other services resulting from SSHOC between one or more of the entities represented in the Governing Board and the service providers will be

signed. Regarding these agreements, it is worth mentioning that **each entity represented in the Governing Board should be free to organise and provide their contribution to the SSH Open Marketplace as they see fit**. Despite the fact that all the SSH ERICs involved in the SSH Open Marketplace are distributed infrastructures, not all have the same internal organisation.

Furthermore, it should be noted that possible **synergies with other SSHOC outputs** - referenced in the SSHOC service catalogue³⁵ and fully detailed as part of the SSHOC Exploitation Plan (to be published later in 2021) - are also under investigation at the time of writing. Two services in particular could be linked to (or even integrated with) the SSH Open Marketplace: the Conversion Hub developed by T3.5 *Data and Metadata Interoperability Hub* and the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit³⁶ developed by T6.4 *Building Expertise: the SSHOC Training Network*. Each of these services have collected solutions for conversions between data and file formats and training materials and will require further curation work after the end of the project. Technical interoperability is under investigation at the time of writing, but curation and editorial tasks could be linked with the one needed for the SSH Open Marketplace. The same editorial team could be in charge of several services, for example. Other integration scenarios were also studied, this time with two CLARIN services - the Language Resource Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry³⁷. Different integration use cases with the Marketplace have been developed, but none of them implemented at the time of writing.

Based on the cost estimation, the possible distribution of funding and legal responsibility presented in this section, sustainability building blocks are taking shape. These dimensions, as well as the missions of the different bodies described in the previous two sections need to be linked to T7.3 work related to data ingestion and to T7.4 work related to the data population and curation. Indeed, given that data quality is the main driver for the uptake of the service, transparency and trust in a service governance devoted to this data quality are key dimensions that have guided the work of this deliverable.

³⁵ SSHOC service catalogue on the SSHOC website: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/service-catalogue> [13.09.2021]

³⁶ SSH Training Discovery Toolkit: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu> [13.09.2021]

³⁷ See Buddenbohm, Stefan, Broeder, Daan, Eisner, Marthe Irene, Illmayer, Klaus, & Durco, Matej. (2020). Collaborative Use Cases between SSH Open Marketplace and the Language Resource Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312708> [13.09.2021]

Governance framework and conclusion

The SSH Open Marketplace’s Governance relies on two important dimensions. First it is built upon two governing bodies: the Governing Board and the Editorial Board, based on an agreed shared governance model between five SSH ERICs (CESSDA ERIC, CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, ESS ERIC, SHARE ERIC). Secondly, this core is expected to be strengthened by users’ contribution to the curation effort through the Contributors Community. For this matter, this deliverable studied the efforts that need to be undertaken to successfully engage the user community in this effort.

The following diagram illustrates the Governance model suggested in this deliverable and each entity’s relations to the other two.

Figure 1: SSH Open Marketplace Governance diagram

Finally, the estimated costs necessary to sustain this SSH Open Marketplace were suggested in the last section. Three types of costs were selected: operational, content, and governing costs. Those costs were estimated based on two potential future scenarios: a silver scenario and a gold one. And several sources of fundings were listed: cash, in-kind contributions, yearly savings, and external funding.

We would like to remind the reader once more that this deliverable has to be read as the first version of the SSH Open Marketplace’ Governance. As the concept development is still ongoing, this document will serve as a basis and future versions could be offered to adapt accordingly. In the course of writing this deliverable, summaries were presented and discussed by the SSHOC Scientific Board and the Project Management Board. The T7.4 team recommends that the terms of the binding agreement be negotiated and signed before the end of the SSHOC project.

References

- Barbot, Laure, Roi, Arnaud, Scharnhorst, Andrea, Ďurčo, Matej, Fischer, Frank, Kalman, Tibor, ... Toth-Czifra, Erzsebet.** (2021, March 19). Towards a concise DARIAH service strategy: 2020 Reflections - White Paper. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621287>
- Barbot, Laure, Moranville, Yoan, Fischer, Frank, Petitfils, Clara, Ďurčo, Matej, Illmayer, Klaus, Parkoła, Tomasz, Wieder, Philipp, & Karampatakis, Sotiris.** (2019). SSHOC D7.1 System Specification - SSH Open Marketplace (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3547649>
- Barbot, Laure, Fischer, Frank, Illmayer, Klaus, Ďurčo, Matej, König, Alexander, Van Uytvanck, Dieter & Larrousse, Nicolas.** (2020). MS.43 - Marketplace - beta release (Version 1.0). Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4785193>
- Buddenbohm, Stefan, Broeder, Daan, Eisner, Marthe Irene, Illmayer, Klaus, & Ďurčo, Matej.** (2020). Collaborative Use Cases between SSH Open Marketplace and the Language Resource Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312708>
- Burrows, Simon and Roe, Glenn,** eds., *Digitizing Enlightenment: Digital Humanities and the Transformation of Eighteenth-Century Studies* (Liverpool: Liverpool University Press)
- Crymble, Adam,** *Technology and the Historian: Transformations in the Digital Age* (Chicago: University of Illinois Press, 2021)
- Dombrowski, Quinn,** What Ever Happened to Project Bamboo?, *Literary and Linguistic Computing*, Volume 29, Issue 3, September 2014, Pages 326–339, <https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/fqu026>
- Dombrowski, Quinn & Rockwell, Geoffrey.** "The Directory Paradox". Forthcoming in *Debates in Digital Humanities: Institutions, Infrastructures at the Interstices*. 2018.
- Edmond, Jennifer & Morselli, Francesca.** What does it mean to sustain a research infrastructure ? Experiences and recommendations from the experience of the CENDARI Project, 2016. http://www.cendari.eu/sites/default/files/CENDARI_D2.4%20Sustainability%20Plan%20final%20%282%29.pdf
- Koureas, Dimitrios & Arvanitidis, Christos & Belbin, Lee & Berendsohn, Walter & Damgaard, Christian et al.** Community engagement: The 'last mile' challenge for European research e-infrastructures, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.2.e9933>
- Rfii - German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures: Building Sustainable Data Services.** Rfii Discussion Paper on the Enhancement of Research Data Infrastructures, Göttingen 2020 <http://www.rfii.de/download/rfii-discussion-paper-on-the-enhancement-of-research-data-infrastructures-september-2020/>

Torma, Martina, Kalaitzi, Vasso, Vipavc Brvar, Irena, Fišer, Darja, Pahor de Maiti, Kristina, Petitfils, Clara, ... Willems, Marieke. (2019). SSHOC D6.1 Community Engagement Strategy (Version v1.0). Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592243>

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